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Assignment 3:

**Evaluation of Social Relationship in Public Spaces
within Communities in Taman Hock Ann**

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Evaluation of Social Relationship in Public Spaces within Communities in Taman Hock Ann

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Keywords: Urban Sustainability, Community Cohesion, Social Integration,
Community Involvement, Sense of Place

Abstract

The main purpose of this research paper is to evaluate the relationship between different groups of cultural community within public places in Taman Hock Ann, interpret the cultural practices and results of sustainable architectural design impact towards the site planning. Due to the advanced technology, vertical community development and fast-paced living manner, relationship within the communities are no more rapport as own families. Sense of defences as the rise of crimes happening in the community also obstructed the bridge within each other. Thus, it would be a great challenge but achieving sustainable development in the built environment necessitates a collaborative approach which able to engage the local communities and stakeholders.

In this research paper, there are three objectives to be investigated in order to consolidate a healthy, well-being and sustainable living environment through curbing the community decentralization and unsecure among the communities. The first objective is to identify the potential trade-offs between sustainable architectural design and the preservation of cultural heritage in relation to the social relationship in public spaces within communities in Taman Hock Ann. It explores how respecting and integrating local customs, traditions and values contribute to better community acceptance. Sense of place authentically represent the local identity when people are in the familiar environment.

This research will identify key factors which hinder the formation of sustainable community and effective strategies for sustainable architectural design integration with existing community infrastructure and resources in Taman Hock Ann to foster cohesion and cooperation. Aligning architectural design with local environmental practices and knowledge can lead to more effective sustainable solutions. Traditional building techniques often take advantage of local climate conditions, promoting natural ventilation, shading, and thermal comfort, which contribute to energy efficiency. Although current building design in track of modernization, sustainable features from custom shall be revitalised.

Furthermore, this research aims to evaluate the relationship between sustainable architectural designs and the overall well-being and mental health impact towards community residents in the context of community cohesion. Sustainable site context is crucial for the habitat liveability, direct related with the wellness of community such as walkability and cyclability. When the community feels a strong cultural connection to the architecture, they are more likely to take pride in preserving and caring for the space.

2.0 Research Issue

2.1 Social Issue in Old Klang Road

2.1.1 Urbanization and Gentrification

The core social issue on site is there are the tendency of locals outflowing from the city if they have sufficient capital. The locals prefer migrate to a better living environment mainly because of they have lost the sense of belongings cultivated during the aged days. During the past, government has forced the occupants to move for urban development, memorable wet market has altered, significant seafood taste has been vanished after the retirement of chef, scene of caring and warmth in this city has evolved. They have lost the living memorial, sustainable relationship and secure environment in this piece of land. The conservative community engagement has been replaced with fast-paced modernization living. Walkable city has been replaced with the hustle and bustle of vehicles, noise of honks and carbon dioxide has covered the serenity bird hamming.

Klang River, has been the main transportation linkage with other district, where the rich natural resources of Malaya, ever recognised as “the only highway through the jungle”. However, those mining and marine transportation route has turned into commercial waste discharge pond. The river has terribly polluted to be of much practical or recreational use. It’s not suitable for body contact — as the river wends downstream due to effluents from sewage treatment plants, commercial and residential centres, industries and workshops, food industries, restaurants, wet markets and squatters (Ding, 2017).

2.1.2 Social Segregation

Rapid development and urbanization may lead to the clustering of certain socio-economic groups in specific areas, potentially resulting in social segregation and limited access to resources and opportunities for some residents. Old Klang Road is developing in a vertical community, especially for the land beside river, this would be a contrast between single-storey traditional Chinese building and high-rise building. The community has been segregated from different culture of living environment.

Housing Disparities also segregate the communities. In certain area, distinct clusters of affluent or lower-income housing led to social separation between different socio-economic groups. The contradiction between these two economic imbalance groups of communities has caused the alienated relationship mainly because of different leisure activities and economic values. Even though meeting, they will have limited interactions.

There is a lack of harmony between different races in Old Klang Road, Malays and Chinese are separated by the Klang River after race conflict of 513 case in 1969 (Times, 2019), many innocent people are died in the massacre. The cultural exchange has blocked by the river, as the barrier within these two races. This historical tragedy has spread the confliction, soon replaced with unrelated practices after elapsed with time.

2.1.3 Community Disengagement

Urban environment changed rapidly, residents may experience a weakening of social ties and community cohesion. This disengagement can lead the lack of participation in civic activities and community initiatives. The domain issue would be the lack of focal point, common interest and activities among the communities. People are isolated due to the breakdown of interaction chain, a sense of unity and belonging within a community can be diminished if members do not engage and collaborate with each other.

Another point of view would be time constraints, where there is a tendency, the communities are developing in a fast-paced circulation. Busy lifestyles, work commitments and family responsibilities can limit the time individuals have available for community involvement. Excessively workload cause the communities do not have mind to foster relationship with their neighbours, as they do not realise the importance of constructing close relationship in their daily lifestyle.

Due to the miss bonding between the communities, sense of belonging and security has evolved in the community. Instead of a community, the occupants treat the place as a shelter and stay place for living only. Apathy between the communities allow disorder to take place in the community, people started to fear of crime, trustiness evolved between the neighbourhoods and thus community cohesion breakdown. During the aged time, Old Klang Road is secure under the safeguarding of community security gang formed to restraint from nearby secret society and junkie. Thus, people are reminiscing those spirit of social integration, unfortunately it has replaced with social distancing relationship, know the neighbours without comprehending.

Dato Hussein Onn has ever mentioned, "In a multicultural country like ours, we need leaders, at all levels of society who are more than just leaders of their respective community. Indeed, to be effective these leaders must be acceptable by all communities. They must always place national interests ahead of sectional and communal interests."

Despite democracy leadership, a healthy community must have common interest which able to bond the whole communities together. Disengagement can lead to a lack of social cohesion, reduced sense of belonging, and limited community development.

2.2 Architectural Issue in Old Klang Road

Figure 1.1 A diverse mix of housing options to promote social interaction and community engagement in Vauban, Freiburg of Germany with open and inclusive site planning which emphasize on community cohesion and sustainable living in the communities.

2.2.1 Gated Community

Gated community consist of strictly controlled entrances for pedestrians, bicycles and automobiles. The community is sustaining with shared amenities to encourage common interest development, but are distinct from intentional communities. Traditionally, it characterized by a closed perimeter of walls and fences. People are engaged in this boundary of gated community. However, it shall not be longer gated as it would disclose the community with another communities, but it is a healthy solution in terms of bonding a stronger community growth and involvement, before stepping into a bigger circle of sustainable community.

Vauban is widely known for its sustainable and inclusive urban planning, which encourages pedestrian-friendly neighbourhoods, green spaces and a car-free zone. The community has gained recognition for its commitment to sustainable living, community cohesion and participatory decision-making. Such sustainable community able to provide tranquillity community living environment, well-being for human nature (Coates, 2013).

2.2.2 Participatory Planning for Community Interaction

Intergenerational interactions shall be encouraged in the community, to bond the relationship between each different area. Parks attract people of varied ages, propose ideal places for inter-generational interactions. Children can play alongside seniors and young parents can connect with experienced parents, creating a sense of community support and understanding. Park as nodes and platform for social communication.

A healthy community shall participate in civil society, public institutions, workplace and in political life. Democracy is crucial by seeking perspective from different groups of people. The fundamental would be respect of social rights and responsibilities for individuals, as when people are really satisfied with the programme, the results of action would be totally different. Vauban provides numerous communal spaces and facilities that facilitate social interactions and community engagement (Committee, 2010). Community centres, shared gardens, playgrounds and public

squares act as meeting points, encouraging neighbours to gather, share experiences and build connections. People are more liveable and appreciate living in self-participatory community.

2.2.3 Mixed and Collaboration Community

Integration community provide the value of diversity and recognizes that a community's strength lies in the collective contributions and experiences of its members. Vauban offers a mix of housing types, including apartments, townhouses, and single-family homes. This diversity encourages a blend of age groups and backgrounds, foster a sense of inclusivity and community cohesion, as inter-generational cultural exchange happening here.

Shared-community facilities serve certain space as focal points where residents can gather, interact and collaborate. These spaces promote social interactions, support the exchange of ideas and inspire a sense of belonging. In addition, mixed communities often celebrate cultural and social events from various backgrounds, provide opportunities for learning about different traditions and bridge understanding between community members. When conflicts arise in a mixed community, there is an opportunity for constructive dialogue and bridge building. Residents can use their diverse perspectives to find creative solutions and strengthen community relationships, avoid disorder rising in the community.

3.0 Literature Review

3.1 Community Cohesion Fostering

When community members have access to shared spaces and activities, it can strengthen social bonds, promote a sense of belonging and promote interactions among the neighbourhood from different backgrounds. To have a strong social relationship, it is fundamental to construct and wider the circle of 'sustainable community' as a socioeconomic model of place, thrive the community with a healthy and resilient living environment. The model of place in which aspirations to create socially inclusive and economically as basis to convince the community stay in the place, in order to have a higher quality of life. It would be an argumentative whether the adoption of 'prosperity' as a guiding principle to building equitable, shall be consider in sustainable futures. When there is a limitation within sustainable environmental and human forms of flourishing inclusivity, prosperity boost a long term social good rather than as short-term financial gain (Woodcraft, January 2018).

Rich in living amenities improve the overall quality of life for residents, making the community more attractive and fostering a sense of collective well-being. High levels of prosperity can reduce competition for limited resources, leading to lower levels of social and economic stress. When individuals feel less threatened by scarcity, they are more likely to cooperate and engage positively with others in the community. Moreover, a thriving community were integrated with good quality housing and infrastructure. Well-designed and well-maintained housing and infrastructure can instil a sense of pride among residents. When people feel proud of their community, they are more likely to actively contribute to its betterment and promote a positive image. As there are more focal points, soon it will facilitate the development of social bonds and a sense of belonging.

The expressions of community cohesion and village identity play crucial roles. Rural response to centrally guided change is examined by exploring manifestations of community cohesion and village identity in a single village (Huseby, 1984). There are strength of relationships, collaboration and shared values among residents within a rural community. It encompasses the sense of togetherness, mutual support, and common purpose that bind individuals together in these settings. Maintaining community cohesion is crucial for the overall well-being and development of rural areas, as it fosters positive interactions, effective problem-solving and a sense of belonging among the communities (Williams, 2020).

In public health, social networks are commonly used to study the transmission of infectious diseases as they provide a map of direct contact for person-to-person transmission (Hegde, 2018). Strong bridging and linking social capital exist in the community from an individual belonging to multiple social groups and networks (E.Kirtley, 1991). Interaction through online within the communities shall be an additional social tool to enhance social integration.

3.2 Sense of Place

Place, as a focus of attachment; Place, as a centre of meaning; Place, as a perception-action process (Christopher M. Raymond, 29 September 2017). Place meanings are subjective but provide connections people with their surroundings, practice sustainable relationship with the people arounds, while also create sense of identity when the practices have become common. Historical, cultural and natural significant landmark shall resonate with the community and instil a sense of pride to the area. Outdoor recreation park or garden would be the perfect choice as people are always attracted by what is happening outside, and close to the nature fresh air for a brief relaxation. It enhances the rate of social communication from the moment stepping out of individual house, out of self-defences boundaries. Through shared experiences and memories, residents develop emotional attachments to these spaces, shaping their perceptions and feelings toward the community as a whole. These place meanings contribute to the overall identity of the community.

Social imaginaries shall incorporate with outdoor recreation park or garden to promote sense of belongings in the area. There are two key topics in this literature focus on attitudinal, differences between local people and newcomers perceived impacts of social development. The foundations for scholarly work about imaginaries have parallels in rural planning literatures, landscape studies, and in rural community change. Similar to Greider and Garkovich (1994, 2) which have studied the symbolic values of rural landscapes in examining how, "Our understandings of nature and of human relationships with the environment are really cultural expressions used to define who we were, who we are and who we hope to be at this place and in this space." Their constructionist approaches explored cultural meanings of landscapes, the symbolism, values and beliefs associated with these and the discursive processes that support the social negotiation of landscape meanings (Jakobic, May 2020).

Public space affects the user's mental health and well-being, and it is direct related to all the health problems that they have or will experience (Bayatli, 2023). Thus, sensory justice, sensory impairments

and sensory placemaking shall be addressed in a well-consideration functionality manner, enhance sensory experiences in public spaces, in order to attract and comfortable the communities to gather at this point.

3.3 Importance of Participatory Planning

Community members shall involve in decision-making process which empowers them to participate in neighbourhoods and outdoor community activities. The common activities must suit different social groups to build trust and cooperation among the occupants.

One of the integrated development strategies to enhance social relationship among the communities are equal opportunities and the right of access to an acceptable standard of living by provide a collaborative platform, consensus, capacity, strategic alliances and the coalitions needed for cooperation. However, it should be specific on what certain actions are required to solve based on different categories of communities. But in the same track, being respected, promote a sense of belongings staying in a community. The presence of social justice and equity shall be in the communities, neighbours look after one another and there is mutual respect. Everybody is treated equally. There are lower levels of crime, drugs addiction and antisocial behaviour which are harmful for the community (Ahmad, 2016).

Isolated communities provide opportunity for the social break down. Reflective to the broken window analogy by Wilson and Kelling (1982), the relationship between disorder and crime: "If a window in a building is broken and is left unrepaired, all the rest of the windows will soon be broken.... One unrepaired broken window is a signal that no one cares, and so breaking more windows costs nothing." There is always a neglect of human characteristics, we don't care about small matters which does not really affect us. However, this would be a terrible mistake which we would regret later. Community vision would be the key point to define whether fear of crime, disorder and crime would be happening in a community. It is most consistent with the traditional view, formulation derives from impressions or stereotypes and illicit responses that are based on general attitudes or values (McKee, August 2001). As such, community cohesion participatory planning must be primary before further uplift the quality of life. Although urban development cannot be restricted, it is crucial to reminisce the Kampung or rural spirit, where the community security gang formed to protect from secret society and junkie surrounding, does not depend on the governmental action.

Social harmony does not occur without effort in these *Rukun Tetangga* communities, but it is an essential ingredient of a successful adjustment of kampung residents to city life. Most kampung residents are conscious of the need to achieve rukun within their own community, and they charge the *Rukun Tetangga* head with coordinating their efforts (Guinness, September 1981). In rural areas, sense of togetherness, mutual support and shared identity among the residents of a rural area are highlighted primary due to their shared-space arrangement and caring practices. Community cohesion is essential for the overall well-being and development of rural areas, as it fosters collaboration, resource sharing and a sense of belonging among the community members.

3.4 Schools as Community Hub

The school should open their doors to the public, embracing a broader community-oriented approach by fostering a sense of belonging among communities. As most of the schools are functioning on the morning session, it would be a potential community point for the communities nearby to appreciate this piece of land. By opening their doors to the broader community, schools create opportunities for residents of all ages to interact and engage in a variety of activities beyond traditional education. This increased interaction fosters a sense of belonging and shared identity among community members. Furthermore, schools are comprehensive with infrastructure and able to provide spaces for community gatherings, meetings, cultural events and recreational activities. Shared resources like libraries, sports facilities and auditoriums become accessible to the community, promoting a collaborative spirit and minimize the needs for duplicating infrastructure.

The process of creating sustainable communities come from many directions in terms of getting people integrated and engaged with the decision-making process for better places and social networking. The advantages of having a school as a community hub for each community taking advantage of their cultural perceptives in the context of urban or rural communities' development these days can be acceptable. However, it is still dependant on a school 's resources, capacity, priorities and objectives such as the education systems (Mansor, 2014).

However, it required partnerships and collaboration. Schools cannot organise alone as they have limited resources. Partnerships with like-minded community members, organisations and service providers are critical to establishing and operating a school as community hub. Facilitating communication, nurturing relationships and developing robust partner-ships requires significant investment of time and resources, but dramatically expands capacity for lasting impacts (Cleveland, 2023). It would be great to consider a cooperation within Nonprofit Organizations after seeking approval from the government if under empowerment region. Partner with nonprofit organizations that focus on education, youth development, arts, sports and social welfare. These organizations can offer specialized programs which are able to enrich the offerings for the community.

No school should be a fortress. Balancing security with an environment that welcomes the community is achievable. Safety is of heightened importance when children mix with adults from the wider community and is best discussed early in design, when both 'hard' and 'soft' security options can be explored. When stakeholders collaborate openly, solutions to security challenges can be found. Well-defined access protocols for different user groups during school times and outside hours should guide security measures. Like in Africa, Black woman as the leaders in the development of social cohesion within predominantly white independent schools through the "Principles of Good Practice", serve as a reminder where the structural boundaries placed by school leaders affect how others perceive and contribute to the shared goals of the organization, the only solution is cohesiveness with the communities (Jean, 2023). Besides, planning for hubs must consider their location relative to other infrastructure, in addition with their physical integration with immediate urban surrounds. The connection of school facilities with social infrastructure networks could enhance community education, health and well-being.

4.0 Research Objective and Methodology

4.1 Research Objective

There are three main objectives for this research:

1. To identify the potential trade-offs between sustainable architectural design and the preservation of cultural heritage in relation to the social relationship in public spaces within communities in Taman Hock Ann.
2. To identify key factors which hinder the formation of sustainable community and effective strategies for integrating sustainable architectural design with existing community infrastructure and public resources to foster community involvement in several community nodes.
3. To evaluate the relationship between sustainable architectural implementation and the overall well-being and mental health impact towards community residents in the context of community cohesion.

4.2 Research Questions

1. How does sustainable architectural design impact community cohesion and social interactions within neighbourhoods?
2. How can sustainable architectural design be tailored to meet the specific needs and preferences of diverse communities, ensuring inclusivity and social cohesion?
3. What policy frameworks and incentives can be put in place to encourage the adoption of sustainable architectural design while prioritizing community cohesion and social integration?

4.3 Methodology

The research methodology on this study topic is to enhance social relationship in public spaces within communities in Taman Hock Ann. To attain this purpose, interview for tangible and observation as additional for intangible facts have implemented in a mixed-mode methodology.

The data collection process involves both quantitative and qualitative methods. To procure accurate quantitative data, the number of social interactions, duration and preferred time for social activities in public spaces, and the frequency of participation in community events are collected with specific figures. Through interview, qualitative would be able to be collected on the residents' perceptions and experiences related to social relationships in public spaces regarding satisfaction levels, frequency of interaction and preferences for specific activities. There will be some facts which placed behind the scene among the communities, which could not be figure out and accumulated in figures.

Taman Hock Ann as Research Study

As a heritage residential area located along Old Klang Road in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, Taman Hock Ann portrayed its potential to study how a multiracial heritage community practice community cohesion in their daily life. This area has a rich history and cultural heritage, the only preserved timber residential after economic development in the Old Klang Road. It is essential to consider the

preservation of these aspects when discussing architectural design and public spaces within the community.

Unfortunately, 25 units have destroyed by blaze at a squatted area in 20 December 2016. Great fortune in this blaze was, rescue personnel have managed to save more than 30 houses in the same vicinity, no people were injured. After verified by the firefighting team, it was primary due to electric short circuit in one of the units, pushing with its timber building material and also close spatial arrangement, moreover under strong winds causing razed in this area.

However, from the blaze, the social relationship within the communities performed, the residents help with each other without defining races or religion, united to put down the fire before the fire brigade arrived. Although it is tradition and compact community, spirit of integration envelope larger scale of communities.

4.3.1 Observation Methodology

4.3.1.1 Observation in Taman Hock Ann, Old Klang Road

The objective of observation is to direct witness and document the behaviour of individuals and groups in public spaces. This includes how people interact, engage in activities and use the available amenities. By observing community behaviour, it would be able to gain valuable insights into the dynamics of social relationships. Moreover, observations provide context to quantitative data. It allows deeper understanding of the nuances of social interactions within specific public spaces, whether people tend to congregate in certain areas or whether particular activities foster socialization.

Objective 1: Identify potential trade-offs between sustainable architectural design and the preservation of cultural heritage in relation to the social relationship in public spaces within communities in Taman Hock Ann.

4.3.1.2 Observation in Public Spaces

Public Spaces is the focal point, which most appropriate to observe the social activities in the communities including the commercial shop lots, food court, plaza, parks and open street seating area. It involves systematically watching and recording the behaviour, activities and interactions of individuals and groups within a public setting. In these public locations, we will able to observe where is the most welcoming location for the community gathering, what kind of environment and space functionality the communities stay the longest, when is the peak hours for the social activities happening in specific location.

Public observation is a valuable technique which carry out in various fields, including sociology, anthropology, urban planning, psychology and environmental studies. In a wide visionary space, individual behaviour of appreciating the public space exposed in direct field of view. The method of community engaging in social activities such as social conversations, gatherings or group activities within familiar neighbourhood or stranger could be defined. Soon, the types of social interactions

take place whether there are people sitting together, playing games or participating during the communal events or common days have to be observed on site.

K88 Food Court is the most crowded food court in Old Klang Road. Officers nearby use to have their lunch here, while during the nights it attracted a lot of locals and youngster gathering at this place. It has become a cuisine focal point, where there provide a series of scrumptious local food here, from snacks until main meal to herbal soups. The attraction of food attack promotes social communication as when there are common activities, there would be more social interaction.

4.3.1.3 Observation in Parking Area

Due to the increase of motorized vehicles, parking lots tend to increase and provide opportunity for the users communicate with each other especially if they are facing the common issues on spot. Setting on parking area for Taman Hock Ann residents and parking lot layout design would be the meet point for different communities to have temporary gathering. In parking area, observe whether their designated spaces for people to gather, socialize or relax have been fulfilled. It relates to the sufficiency of social pocket spaces and infrastructure in public spaces. For example, some parking areas include seating, picnic tables or green spaces for the community to have social interaction.

Furthermore, observe whether car park is in accessible design, which promote inclusivity and allows a wider range of people to participate in social activities. The parking area must provide specific spaces and comfortable environment for the society activities, or else people are not willing to stay longer in a muggy space.

Car Park behind Old Klang Road Wet Market and random car park area in Taman Hock Ann spot to be the observation locations as there are the most common car parks where people from outside intend to visit Taman Hock Ann or its residents to buy their necessities in the Wet Market and park their vehicles just behind the building.

4.3.2 Interview Methodology

Through interview, social relationship in Taman Hock Ann able to be evaluated as in-depth insights are provided by the interviewee's thoughts, experiences and perspectives about the current levels of social relationship among the communities.

Interviewee:

Different races of residents in Taman Hock Ann, Local residents who stay more than 30 years in PPR residential apartment, visitors in Old Klang Road Wet Market.

Interview Objective:

Understand the social activities in Taman Hock Ann influenced by surrounding site context, further explore the current community relationship, cultural human flows and behaviour among public spaces in Kampung Pasir Lama Pasar Malam.

Objective 1: Identify potential trade-offs between sustainable architectural design and the preservation of cultural heritage in relation to the social relationship in public spaces within communities in Taman Hock Ann.

1. In your opinion, are there having accessible infrastructure and public spaces within the community for the social benefits?
2. In times of leisure, which place or activities you will visit for emotional support or relief?
3. Are you involved in any community groups, clubs or organizations in the Taman Hock Ann community and its public spaces? How often do you visit them?
4. Are there specific public spaces in Taman Hock Ann that you particularly enjoy spending time in? What makes them special to you?
5. What types of social activities or gatherings do you usually participate in within the community's public spaces?
6. How often are community events or gatherings held in public spaces here? Can you share your experiences attending these events?

Objective 2: Identify key factors which hinder the formation of sustainable community and effective strategies for integrating sustainable architectural design with existing community infrastructure and public resources to foster community involvement in several community nodes.

7. How would you describe the diversity within Taman Hock Ann in terms of the people who use these public spaces? Do you think the spaces are inclusive?
8. Do you feel safe and comfortable when using the public spaces in the community? Are there any safety concerns or improvements you'd like to see?
9. Are there any cultural or heritage elements in the public spaces that contribute to social interactions or community identity?
10. In your opinion, what initiatives or improvements could be made to further promote social relationships within Taman Hock Ann's public spaces?

11. What do you envision for the future of public spaces in Taman Hock Ann? Are there any ideas for enhancing their role in fostering social relationships?

Objective 3: Identify the nature of social interactions in the public spaces and utilization patterns of public spaces, in order to promote community cohesion.

12. How frequent and what purposes for which residents of Taman Hock Ann use various public spaces such as parks, plazas, markets, and community centres?

13. Is that park assessable for senior citizen and disabilities? What are the types of social interactions taking place within public spaces?

14. Are people engaging in recreational activities, socializing, or using the spaces for specific purposes like sports or cultural events?

5.0 Research Findings

Throughout my research, I have discovered that there are a number of people has discussed with the community issue occurred in Klang Valley, but not in the Taman Hock Ann area as this heritage community has been neglected by the current urbanization development.

There is some social connectivity in Taman Hock Ann, but the interactions within the communities are limited, people are gathering and celebrate together for special festival events only.

5.1 Demographics and Activities in relation to Site Context of Taman Hock Ann

Races	Percentage of Occupants in Taman Hock Ann (%)
Malay	10
Chinese	40
Foreigner	50

Figure 1.2 Ratio of different races in Taman Hock Ann communities, create a multicultural exchange society.

Figure 1.3 Site condition in Taman Hock Ann, the only current leftover timber residential area in Old Klang Road, social integration living area with Malays, Chinese and foreigners.

Figure 1.4 Above highlighted red boundary as Taman Hock Ann residential area. Marking of religious practices, ethnical celebration and community activity's location. There are a lot of potential community focal point, but not really appreciate by the community, those spots shall be activated.

1. Taman Hock Ann occupants will celebrate Chinese New Year at Pasar Batu 4 1/2 Jalan Klang Lama (1969)
2. Full Gospel Assembly (1979) gather surrounding Christian here, congested traffic in these route during every Sunday.
3. Scott Garden become the nearest community focal point for Taman Hock Ann occupants, while also celebrating Hari Raya Aidilfitri, Chinese New Year and Deepavali here.
4. Klang River Festival celebrate artistry, heritage, community and the rich biodiversity of the Klang River, gather the community during this festival.
5. Masjid Jamek Al Khadijiah allows Muslim to worship here, social interaction in this location.

5.2 Social Activities Analysis in Taman Hock Ann

Type of Activities	Location of Activities	Number of People	Duration and Preferred Period of Activities	Frequency of participation in specific activities
Communication within different races and age groups	<u>Cultural</u> Old Klang Road Wet Market	130 Vendors 58 Visitors (64% Chinese, 25% India, 11% Foreigner)	Most crowded during peak hours 9.15am.	Most of the families visit one day per week to buy groceries
Worship	<u>Religion</u> Masjid Jamek Al Khadijah	53 believers	Most believers gather at Masjid during Friday afternoon prayer.	Believers visit here three times in a day.
Worship	<u>Religion</u> Full Gospel Assembly Kuala Lumpur	228 believers	Most crowded during every Sunday morning.	Most frequent one to two days per week
Eating in food court	<u>Community</u> K88 Food Court	55 visitors during afternoon 135 visitors during night	Average visitors will stay 1 hour here to enjoy their meal and chitchatting.	Neighbours visit here average 2 days in a week.
Pasar Malam	<u>Community</u> Kampung Pasir Lama Pasar Malam	70 to 80 visitors in the Pasar Malam	Most crowded during peak hour within 8 to 9pm.	One day per week, most of the locals nearby buy groceries here.
Waiting for bus	<u>Infrastructure</u> Bus Stop for Rapid KL bus	Average 5-7 person per trip during normal hours	Every 15 minutes will have one trip bus.	1. Officers who use as transport visit here every weekday. 2. People visit public spaces in other region in average 1-2 times per week.

Figure 1.5 Data collection from interview and observation on 17th of September 2023

5.3 Social Activities Pattern Chart Analysis in Taman Hock Ann

Objective 1: Identify potential trade-offs between sustainable architectural design and the preservation of cultural heritage in relation to the social relationship in public spaces within communities in Taman Hock Ann.

Objective 2: Identify key factors which hinder the formation of sustainable community and effective strategies for integrating sustainable architectural design with existing community infrastructure and public resources to foster community involvement in several community nodes.

6.0 Discussion

From the result of the study, it can be proved that there are still weak in public accessibility due to loss of connection between infrastructure and public amenities, lack of community events in Taman Hock Ann and surrounding communities and poor social interaction in the communities after 513 tragedy and high-rise development in Old Klang Road. However, Taman Hock Ann is still a welcoming residential area, performing social inclusivity to all members of the community, regardless of age, background or socioeconomic status.

First, the level of community cohesion and interaction could be regarded as medium as there show enthusiasm and integrity from my conversation with Taman Hock Ann's residents. However, prejudice still present this community, I have noticed that the locals seldom communicate with the foreigners. Among Malaysian community members, they are actively engaging with one another in these spaces. Unfortunately, there are barriers to interaction between Malaysian and foreigner. But, they still tolerate the cultural differences and stay peacefully in one area.

Pasar Batu 4 1/2 Jalan Klang Lama, a cultural heritage social focal point which started since 1969 act as vital role of public spaces for Taman Hock Ann and surrounding communities. It is not merely a market, but communal areas to foster social relationships. The spaces are well-utilized by the community as it serves as meeting points or hubs for social activities despite commercial purposes. There are regular community events and activities within Pasar Batu 4 1/2, such as cultural festivals, art exhibitions or food fairs. These events can bring people together and foster a sense of belonging. By providing ample seating and communal areas where people can sit, eat and have face-to-face interactions at the same time. It would more inclusive if a community market association committee has formed to enhance the social relationship while also uplift business relationship between both vendors and residents. This group can work together to plan and implement social and community-building initiatives.

The key factors which hinder the formation of sustainable community in Taman Hock Ann would be lack of community engagement. Communities struggle to become sustainable as there is insufficient engagement and participation from residents. When people are not actively involved in decision-making and community initiatives, it becomes challenging to implement sustainable practices. As in Taman Hock Ann, they should have some communities event, which can initiate from gotong-royong, which could improve their social relationship meanwhile live in a healthier and comfortable environment. Gotong-royong is a cost-effectiveness community activity, which help to build a consolidate groups of people. Furthermore, cultural norms and social dynamics can hinder the adoption of sustainable practices. For instance, deeply ingrained practices that are not sustainable may be challenging to alter.

Last but not least, there are terribly lack of comprehensive public amenities and infrastructure with proper accessibility from Taman Hock Ann. Pedestrian falls in risk when they are forced to access certain location. The connection of bridges and walkways have to be proposed, to ensure they meet the needs of the community and provide safe and convenient access. Safety measures have to be implemented, such as railings, lighting and signage for the safety of users, especially during nighttime

period. From my site observation, there are some interactions within the users, most of them asking about the time for bus arriving, and I realised that most of the user would prefer to have a seat while waiting at the bus stop. However, there are few seats which are in wet and rusty condition. At such condition, user would prefer to stand rather than clean it and have a seat. Thus, constant maintenance shall be held to ensure the functionability of public infrastructure. It shall be considered to arrange seating tend to a face-to-face or circular manner to facilitate social interaction. Moreover, ensure that the bus stop is well-lit and safe, creating a comfortable environment for social interactions, especially when the weather has turned gloomy.

Aspect	Social Relationship in Public Spaces in Taman Hock Ann		
	Weak	Medium	Strong
Public Accessibility	✓		
Sense of Belongings		✓	
Community Involvement		✓	
Sense of Place		✓	
Social Activities		✓	
Community Events	✓		
Community Inclusivity	✓		
Safety and Comfort in Public Spaces		✓	
Community Identity		✓	
Community Initiatives	✓		
Social Relationship		✓	

Figure 1.6 Levels of community cohesion for residents in Taman Hock Ann.

7.0 Conclusion

From the research findings and analysis, I would conclude that Taman Hock Ann is rich with cultural religious village where the communities are able to build a cohesive community by celebrating special festivals together, interact in several nodes and practice different religious with respectful and consciousness manner. In summary, the evaluation of social relationships within Taman Hock Ann underscores a community characterized by cultural diversity, strong interpersonal bonds and collaborative efforts. While challenges such as generational differences and communication barriers between locals and foreigners, the overall atmosphere remains one of shared identity and a willingness to work together for the betterment of the community. Efforts to address these challenges and enhance inclusivity will contribute to a more resilient and vibrant social fabric within Taman Hock Ann.

Diversity in public spaces within the communities are wide. Taman Hock Ann's public spaces cater to a diverse range of activities and interests. Parks, community centres and markets serve as hubs for social interaction, bring together individuals from various backgrounds and age groups. In short, the

social integration points are there, but malfunction or underutilized, social infrastructure is the key to consolidate a strong bonding social relationship in the urban sustainability context. Public spaces in Taman Hock Ann encourage interactions among different generations. Elderly residents can be seen engaging in activities alongside children and adults, which helps bridge generational gaps and fosters mutual understanding. Public spaces shall serve as platforms for community engagement and participation. When residents actively contribute to the upkeep and enhancement of these spaces, create a sense of place and pride in their neighbourhood, social integration formed as residents are more liveable and appreciate the moments celebrating with the society.

The evaluation of social relationships in public spaces within communities in Taman Hock Ann highlights the significance of these spaces in fostering social cohesion, community engagement and inclusivity. By providing spaces that cater to various interests and age groups, the community has successfully created a thriving environment where residents from different backgrounds come together. While there are challenges to address, the overall outlook is positive. Furthermore, Taman Hock Ann's approach to public spaces can serve as a model for other communities seeking to strengthen social bonds and create vibrant neighbourhoods. It is crucial for the community continue invest in these spaces, ensuring they remain inclusive, accessible and well-maintained to sustain the positive social relationships they facilitate.

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